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M6.9. REPORT ON FINAL REVIEW OF FAIR COMPETENCIES LANDSCAPE

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Introduction

This report is a milestone of the FAIRsFAIR project, the purpose of the milestone is to provide a periodic review of FAIR competencies landscape during the course of the project. The report summarises some of the models of competence centre support available to communities of practice at the national, regional and EOSC level that have become available or changed in the 18 months since the initial landscaping activities conducted by FAIRsFAIR in 2019 and reported in D6.1 Overview of needs for competence centres¹.

Competence Centre definition and characterisation

FAIRsFAIR conducted a landscape analysis during its first year (2019) looking at the FAIR competence landscape.

The FAIRsFAIR D6.1 report, Overview of needs for competence centres, defined a competence centre as *“a shared hub of expertise in implementing FAIR data stewardship principles, offering leadership, coordination and cataloguing services to connect relevant people, guidance, learning resources and curricula in different thematic areas”*. This definition was expanded on in the report D6.2, Initial Core Competence Centre Structures², which focused on three activity areas: **advisory, harmonisation and dissemination** and where we outlined key characteristics as:

- Defines the organisation’s mission to support research data management or stewardship, including the adoption and implementation of FAIR and open principles.

¹ Herterich, Patricia, Davidson, Joy, Whyte, Angus, Molloy, Laura, Matthews, Brian, & Kayumbi Kabeya, Gabin. (2019). D6.1 Overview of needs for competence centres (1.0). FAIRsFAIR. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361524>

² Newbold, Elizabeth, Kayumbi Kabeya, Gabin, Matthews, Brian, Davidson, Joy, Herterich, Patricia, Whyte, Angus, & Molloy, Laura. (2020). D6.2 Initial Core Competence Centre Structures (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361649> p.12

- Provides one or more services to support research data management or stewardship for identified users or audiences, user communities [and provides metadata about the service to an EOSC catalogue].
- Identifies the scope of the competences it aims to develop, in fulfilling its mission.
- Documents the training or other methods it uses to develop competences.
- Applies a CC-BY or CC-0 license to its learning resources or other outputs.
- Makes learning resources metadata findable through a local and/or third-party catalogue or discoverable through third-party catalogues.
- Makes learning resources accessible under clear conditions, and described using community-agreed terms.
- Advises its users on the assessment of FAIR data stewardship activities and outputs.
- Plans for the sustainability and continuity of its operations.
- Leads or participates in FAIR policy development.

Developments in the landscape

During 2020 an [EOSC Working Group on Skills and Training](#)³ was established in recognition of the importance of the skills and capabilities agenda across stakeholder communities. The Working Group report on Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science⁴ reviewed the competence centre concept, conducting 23 interviews to provide case studies for review of the approaches around the priorities for competence centres to provide advisory services, enable harmonisation and support dissemination.

The EOSC WG focused around the services commonly associated with competence centres⁵:

- Provision of training
- Data services or research software engineering
- Guidance resources and advisory services
- Development of communities
- Catalogues of resources, services or policies
- Creation or dissemination of standards
- Evaluation and assessment services

³ <https://eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/skills-training-working-group>

⁴ Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science, Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, DOI: 10.2777/59065 chapter 4 page 27 <https://doi.org/10.2777/59065>

⁵ Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science, Report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group, DOI: 10.2777/59065 chapter 4 page 29 <https://doi.org/10.2777/59065>

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- Hub for collaboration between stakeholders

Whilst the characterisation of competence centres has largely consolidated around the three areas of advisory, harmonisation and dissemination, the implementation of this has considerable variation drawing on elements of characterisation defined by both FAIRSFair and the EOSC Working Group.

The original [spreadsheet](#) from the FAIRSFair work on Competence Centre Characterisation (D6.1 report, Overview of needs for competence centres) has been [updated](#) to include more recent competence centres.

Among other roles, competence centres are expected to operate effectively in disseminating their expertise to their user communities through outreach and training programmes. Likewise, communication between competence centres with similar targeted audiences would minimise duplication of efforts and help organisations benefit from sharing mutual experience. The outreach approach of organisations listed in the [spreadsheet](#) varies according to the nature of the organisation and type of services provided. Most consist of deposited online resources (including reports, newsletters, guidelines, training material) but others provide additional communication forms that extend to face-to-face training sessions, workshops, and seminars. A number of organisations stretch their community engagement to providing an interactive platform for formal and informal exchange where experts and users share knowledge. The Italian competence centre for EOSC, the ICDI with its Open Science cafe is one of them.

In the following section we summarise some of the initiatives that are contributing to the FAIR competence landscape, many of which have been supported by or developed in the context of the EOSC.

EOSC Landscape/Projects

INFRAEOSC 5b projects are the subgroup that includes the four regional projects covering all corners of Europe, as well as the thematic project ExPaNDS. They were not characterised in the original spreadsheet as the projects had only just started.

[EOSC Synergy](#) expands the capacity and capabilities of the EOSC by leveraging the experience, effort and resources of national publicly funded digital infrastructures in a coherent way, therefore acting also as an incentive for national resource providers. EOSC-synergy extends

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coordination to Czech Republic, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain, and the UK. Part of the project is to support the development of capability and skills for EOSC stakeholders and is providing a training programme and infrastructure including an e-learning platform and a portfolio of tools and platforms. Its courses and services are delivered on the [EOSC Synergy Learn web site](#).

[EOSC Pillar](#) aims to coordinate national open science efforts across Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, and Italy, ensuring their contribution to the development and readiness for the implementation of the EOSC. The vision is that national open science initiatives, either existing or under development, are the key to involve live user communities and research infrastructures in the creation of EOSC. EOSC Pillar are providing a [research data management training and support catalogue](#).

[ExPaNDS](#) is the EOSC Photon and Neutron Data Service. It expands, accelerates and supports the data management and data services provided through the EOSC for major national Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructures (PaN RIs) in delivering world-leading science. The project follows the FAIR principles and aims to harmonise efforts to migrate data analysis workflows to EOSC platforms, enabling them to be shared in a uniform way. Working in collaboration with PaNOSC, ExPaNDS are providing a [training catalogue and learning platform](#) as well as delivering training on FAIR principles.

[NI4OS](#) aims to be a core contributor to the EOSC service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness at the European level for enabling global open science. The project supports the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries instilling FAIR principles within the community. Alongside the provision of technical and policy support for the on-boarding of service providers into EOSC, there is a [training platform](#) to support both end user and national capacity building training activities.

[EOSC Nordic](#) aims is to facilitate the coordination of EOSC relevant initiatives taking place in Finland, Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Iceland, Estonia, Lithuania, and Latvia and exploit synergies to achieve greater harmonisation at policy and service provisioning levels across these countries, in compliance with EOSC agreed standards and practices. The support includes a [training library](#) and a series of workshops.

ESFRI Clusters

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) cluster projects were launched in 2019 in order to implement interfaces to integrate computer and data management solutions, to create cross-border and open cooperation spaces and to promote clouds via the EOSC portal for a larger user community. Many of these clusters have a remit in the delivery of skills and competences to support FAIR data practices.

SSHOC aims to provide an open cloud for social sciences and humanities where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for users. This open cloud aims to be a part of the EOSC. The consortium covers the whole data cycle, from data creation and curation, to optimal data reuse, and can address training and advocacy to increase actual reuse of data. Developments include the SSH [Training Discovery Toolkit](#), webinars and workshops as well as train-the trainer bootcamps.

ENVRI FAIR implements the ENVRI-hub - a virtual, federated machine-to-machine interface to access environmental data and services provided by the contributing RIs. The complete set of thematic data services and tools are incorporated into the EOSC service catalogue, through the EOSC-hub Marketplace. A key activity is for training and capacity building around the FAIR Principles and their implementation. To facilitate this, there is an ENVIRA-FAIR [training catalogue](#) and [training platform](#) as well as a series of events.

PaNOSC helps the Photon and Neutron ESFRIs to adopt and implement data management, simulation and analysis services, and to make their open data available to the EOSC. The project is providing access to training through the training portal⁶ for the photon and neutron community incorporating an [e-learning platform](#), a [training catalogue](#), workflows and events.

ESCAPE brings together ESFRI facilities of astronomy, astroparticle & particle physics into a single EU collaborative cluster. ESCAPE presents a strong component of training - aiming at attracting and educating young scientists towards Open Science and data stewardship, in using the developed tools and methodology ESCAPE also supports the [Open-source Scientific Software](#)

⁶ Training portal <https://pan-training.hzdr.de>

[and Service Repository](#) (OSSR) as a major component of RI data to be preserved and exposed in EOSC through dedicated catalogues.

EOSC Life brings together biological and medical RIs to create an open collaborative space for digital biology. It aims to publish FAIR life science data resources for cloud use creating an ecosystem of innovative tools in EOSC and enabling groundbreaking data-driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC. Working with the EOSC Life community hands on [training](#) and resources will be developed to support operators and users to develop the skills needed to enable effective research data access and preservation.

Through a series of workshops the **FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force** looked at and reported on the [Turning FAIR into Reality \(TFiR\)](#)⁷ recommendations. The third report is available and highlights the status of the activities undertaken within the projects in the EOSC Landscape⁸. In relation to training and skills the TFiR pillar 4 on skills and capacity building identifies the needs for training and professionalising data stewardship. From the Synchronisation Force workshops, we have a good overview of activities that are taking place to develop these skills with multiple activities concentrating on delivering skills training for data stewards and researchers. As well as the delivery of training there are developments of training materials for re-use, training catalogues for the discovery of training materials and learning management platforms for self directed learning.

European National/Regional initiatives

In addition to activities carried out under the formal umbrella of EOSC or EU funded projects there have been a number of national or regional initiatives focused on FAIR data, data stewardship and the practical implementation of embedding data stewards and stewardship competencies into institutions. The following provides a brief summary of some of these activities⁹.

⁷ Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data. Turning FAIR into Reality (2018), European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

⁸ Grootveld, Marjan, Hodson, Simon, Pittonet Gaiarin, Sara, Davidson, Joy, & Dillo, Ingrid. (2021). D5.6 Report 3 of the Synchronisation Force (V1.0_DRAFT). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336658>. The workshop notes and spreadsheets provide details of the activities undertaken but the different projects and can be found linked to the Zenodo record for the report.

⁹ The analysis carried out by the EOSC WG has not been repeated or duplicated; the summaries below either include new initiatives or provide updates on the ones already mentioned or ones not included in

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Austria

FAIR Data Austria is a national initiative “to strengthen knowledge transfer between universities, industry, and society and supports the sustainable implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)”¹⁰. The project runs for two years from January 2020 until December 2022, with 6 partner institutions and 23 associated partners. In June 2021, FAIR Office Austria was launched with the task of working across stakeholders to support the exchange of FAIR topics in Austria and is linked to the global GO FAIR initiative.

So far, the key challenges that have been identified include a high demand for data science and programming skills and the lack of clearly defined roles and responsibilities around data stewardship coupled with different expectations across institutions¹¹ of what a data steward is and does. Work of the FAIR Data Austria initiative includes defining data stewards models, profiles, competencies and training in the Austrian context including running a webinar series and work on developing competences via a certificate course for data stewards¹² which is planned to run in 2022.

Recognising the differences within institutions FAIR Data Austria have identified different models of interaction ranging from a single person or post, through to a network or centre. The long term goal is to establish a self assessment tool for institutions to use to identify a suitable model of support for that institution where they can match requirements and organisation context to existing solutions.

Belgium (Flanders)

Institutional and national initiatives have developed in tandem with initial activities starting in individual Universities, e.g. the University of Ghent developed a small team of data stewards drawing on work that had started in the Netherlands.

the ESOC WG report. This is not intended to be a comprehensive review but to highlight the range of initiatives.

¹⁰ [About FAIR Data Austria - Cluster Forschungsdaten](https://forschungsdaten.at/en/fair-data-austria/about-fair-data-austria/)
<https://forschungsdaten.at/en/fair-data-austria/about-fair-data-austria/> (accessed October 2021)

¹¹ Reichmann, Stefan. (2020). Data Stewardship Profile - Results from a survey of 6 Austrian research-performing institutions. <https://doi.org/10.25365/phaidra.242>

¹² Tereza Kalová. (2021, October 1). 5 Data Stewards per 100 Researchers?! The Development of a Certificate Course "Data Steward" at the University of Vienna. Open Science Fair 2021 (OSFair2021). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5544024>

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The Flemish Open Science Board (FOSB)¹³ was set up late 2019 and formally established in February 2020 to support research organisations transition to open science. As part of this initiative a need for data stewards was identified and funding was made available to include dedicated funds for the hiring of data stewards. The model is a decentralised approach to support researchers in the workplace.

There is an ongoing need to develop a growth plan for data stewards and provide the relevant infrastructure for structured training as well as moving towards a shared understanding of data stewards roles and competences.

Denmark

The DeIC (Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation) is a unit under the Danish Agency for Science and coordinates digital infrastructure for the eight Danish universities. In collaboration with GO FAIR DeIC coordinates Danish participation in Nordic and European e-infrastructure organisations and projects¹⁴. Focuses include the National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark¹⁵, as well as strengthening the dissemination and financing of good RDM practices.

Challenges have included; a need for culture change as the practices of open and FAIR data are not commonplace in many fields, as well as concerns around funding. Research groups need support to define their own implementation of the FAIR principles. Furthermore Wildgaard et al (2020) report recommended the creation of a “Data Steward network to increase future involvement in DS training and share learning outcomes and experiences between institutions across all relevant sectors”¹⁶

¹³ [Flemish Open Science Board \(FOSB\) opgericht | Departement EWI \(ewi-vlaanderen.be\)](#)

¹⁴ About the DeIC <https://www.deic.dk/en/about-deic> (accessed 25 october 2021)

¹⁵ Wildgaard, Lorna, Vlachos, Evgenios, Nondal, Lars, Larsen, Asger Væring, & Svendsen, Michael. (2020). National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3609516>

¹⁶ Wildgaard, Lorna, Vlachos, Evgenios, Nondal, Lars, Larsen, Asger Væring, & Svendsen, Michael. (2020). National Coordination of Data Steward Education in Denmark: Final report to the National Forum for Research Data Management (DM Forum) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3609516> (Page 28)

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Estonia

The Digital Agenda 2020 for Estonia (EIS) set by the Estonian government, and reviewed in 2018, included among other objectives the improvement of public sector capacity to use data analytics and data science, including respective awareness and skills. Activities are by and large conducted under the umbrella of their National Statistic Office and aim at transforming Statistics Estonia¹⁷ into a public-sector competence centre for data governance and data science. At the national level, the development of professional Data Stewards (authorised enablers) is to be considered within the context of that national agenda¹⁸.

Germany

GO UNITE the german chapter of the GO FAIR Implementation Network Data Stewardship Competence Centers (DSCC) launched in October 2020 with an initial kick-off meeting that identified the following requirements for the project¹⁹:

Identification of relevant RDM topics and initiatives that require stronger networking within the community and between initiatives, with the aim to avoid duplicate work. For example: a method for documenting all existing materials (with a common metadata scheme) in order to obtain a complete overview of all existing RDM training material and programs.

Evaluation of current RDM processes and workflows, with the aim to develop a description model for RDM demands. As well as, a stronger connection to the GO FAIR DSCC, including mutual guest contributions, with the aim of increasing networking opportunities between the participating countries.

Ireland

At a national level the National Open Research Forum (NORF) was established in 2017 to drive the agenda for open research in Ireland. A National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment²⁰ was launched in July 2019 including actions on enabling FAIR research

¹⁷ <https://e-estonia.com/statistics-estonia-data-enables-informed-decision-making/>

¹⁸ <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/undataforum/webinars/docs/Estonia-data-stewardship.pdf>

¹⁹ Pragmatic – Concrete – Community-driven: The Credo of GO UNI
<https://www.go-fair.org/2021/02/23/pragmatic-concrete-community-driven-the-credo-of-go-uni/>
(accessed on 25th Oct 2021)

²⁰ [National Framework on the Transition to an Open Research Environment - Digital Repository of Ireland \(dri.ie\)](https://dri.ie/national-framework-on-the-transition-to-an-open-research-environment)

data as well as setting an agenda for skills and competencies to support open research. Since then a draft landscape report²¹ has been produced which reviews progress against the Framework.

NORF provides a forum and framework to bring together institutions in Ireland working on open research including research funders, research performing organisations and Higher Education Institutions. As in other regions support for research data management and FAIR is provided at a local organisation or institutional level, often based within libraries, with provisions varying nationally. There is an emerging data stewardship community²² with ongoing work in institutions and the development of data stewardship roles. The first training for data stewards was undertaken in 2018²³ and in 2021 over 30 people from 28 institutions, participated in data stewardship training in conjunction with FAIRSFair²⁴. Whilst the draft landscape report notes that there is a key gap in the provision of “access to targeted and accredited training programmes”, not just for researchers but also for the associated support services²⁵, there are areas of good practice and progress supported by an evolving network of data stewards.

Italy

The ICDI is composed of representatives of major Italian Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures that look at promoting synergies at the national level while strengthening Italy’s presence in addressing European and global challenges including the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the European Data Infrastructure (EDI) and High Performance Computing. Under the ICDI a competence centre²⁶ for open science, FAIR and EOSC has been set up. An action plan has been published²⁷ which sets out the mission and objectives of the Competence

²¹ National Research Forum Ireland (NORF, National Open Research Landscape, March 2021, version 0.6 [NORF landscape report: draft for public comment - Google Docs](#)

²² [A focus on... the emerging role of 'Data Steward' in Ireland | Digital Repository Ireland \(dri.ie\)](#)

²³ [HRB to offer training opportunity to create Ireland's first FAIR data stewards](#)

²⁴ [NORF collaborates with FAIRSFair and EOSC Synergy on Data Stewardship training | National Open Research Forum](#)

²⁵ National Research Forum Ireland (NORF, National Open Research Landscape, March 2021, version 0.6 Section 3, Enabling FAIR research data page 38. [NORF landscape report: draft for public comment - Google Docs](#) (accessed October 2021)

²⁶ [Competence Centre \(icdi.it\)](#)

²⁷ Lazzeri, Emma, Tanlongo, Federica, Pavone, Gina, Alpi, Federico, Ansuini, Alessio, Bertazzon, Elis, Bonaccorsi, Daniele, Cappelluti, Federica, Casati, Sara, Castelli, Donatella, Cippitani, Roberto, Colcelli, Valentina, Costantini, Alessandro, Cozzini, Stefano, Degl'Innocenti, Emiliano, Di Donato, Francesca, Di Giorgio, Sara, Fava, Ilaria, Fiore, Sandro, ... Zane, Donatella. (2021). ICDI Competence Centre for Open

Centre. The vision is for a pooling of competence and expertise providing training and support, tools and services, sharing of good practice and the professionalism of data stewardship. Initial activities have begun with a series of webinars tailored for the Italian research community.

Netherlands

The landscape in the Netherlands is perhaps one of the most developed. The Netherlands favours a “bottom up” approach in a national setting with funding provided by the Dutch Government directly to the Universities. Initial work focused on looking at data stewardship as professional role in life sciences²⁸. The work was continued in the Dutch National Programme Open Science culminating in their report on professionalising data stewardship²⁹.

A national programme of open science supports the formation of Local Digital Competence Centres. Universities, medical centres, NWO and KNAW institute organisations can apply for one off impulse funding for the establishment of locally based digital competence centres with the intention to stimulate further developments. Both institutional and thematic competence centre models are encouraged. Additionally there is a network of experts that work together to connect policy and practice in research data management through the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM)³⁰. Collaboration and community building is an important element in regard to capacity building. For example, the health data stewardship community brings together healthcare data stewards to support each other's work to share knowledge so that each institute is not starting from scratch.

Poland

The Bridge of Data project was launched in 2018 and will run until September 2021, with the aim of creating a competence centre providing a range of expertise, training and support

Science, FAIR and EOSC - Mission, Strategy and Action Plan. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5512638>

²⁸ Salome Scholtens, Mijke Jetten, Jasmin Böhmer, Christine Staiger, Inge Slouwerhof, Marije van der Geest, & Celia W.G. van Gelder. (2019). Final report: Towards FAIR data steward as profession for the lifesciences. Report of a ZonMw funded collaborative approach built on existing expertise. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3474630>

²⁹ Mijke Jetten, Marjan Grootveld, Annemie Mordant, Mascha Jansen, Margreet Bloemers, Margriet Miedema, & Celia W.G. van Gelder. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>

³⁰ [Homepage | Landelijk Coördinatiepunt Research Data Management \(lcrdm.nl\)](https://www.lcrdm.nl)

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related to Open Science³¹. As well as a repository dedicated to collect, store and enable access to datasets from Polish universities³².

The Polish Data Steward School launched in 2020, with the second edition of the school running in September 2021, training a total of 24 data stewards across the two events. Additionally, Gdansk University and FAIRSFair hosted a 3 day three day train-the-trainer Data Steward Workshop. Attendees identified key challenges and improvements required in order to support research activities in their respective institutions including; a lack of advisory services and trainings on RDM and DMPs, as well as a need for a local peer network³³.

Serbia

The University of Belgrade received EOSC Co-Creation Funding to boost EOSC readiness in the creation of a scalable model for capacity building in research data management³⁴ and to address some of the gaps that have been observed including those of professional data stewards or other professionals with suitable competences and skills. The main goal of the project was to create a model to support local capacity building in research data management. A key issue that the project addressed was the tailoring of activities to meet the needs of the south slavic speaking regions and the lack of training materials in the local language. The aim was to create a set of resources and the main output was a web portal [Serbia.RDM - Home \(open.ac.rs\)](https://open.ac.rs). Additional activities at the University of Belgrade Computer Centre include training and capacity building³⁵ and delivery of end user training in collaboration with NI4OS.

Sweden

In Sweden, the [Swedish National Data Service](#) (SND) mission is to create possibilities for researchers to describe, share, and reuse research data. Through its network, SND's main targets are HEIs and other Research Organisation. Organisations in SND network, inter alia

³¹ [About the project | Gdańsk University of Technology \(pg.edu.pl\)](#) (accessed 26th Oct 2021)

³² [The nature of the project - Bridge of Knowledge and Bridge of Data Projects \(pg.edu.pl\)](#) (accessed 26th Oct 2021)

³³ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/articles-publications/fairsfair-codata-rda-data-steward-training-series-poland> (accessed 26th Oct 2021)

³⁴ Miljković, Nadica, Ševkušić, Milica, Lazarević B., Ljiljana, Vučkovac, Obrad, & Otašević, Vladimir. (2021). TECHNICAL REPORT for Co-creation activity #79 - Boosting EOSC readiness: Creating a scalable model for capacity building in RDM (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4696596>

³⁵ Ana Dordevic. (2021, September 23). Building capacity for Open Science through institutional repository training. Open Science Fair 2021 (OSFair2021). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5543994>

Swedish higher education institutions and public research institutes, have access to support such as advice, training materials, and tools for research data management. The SND provides training and information, develops tools and services that facilitate the management, sharing, and reuse of research data. The SND systems are designed to make it as easy as possible for users to find, reuse, and share research data.

However, it is important to emphasize that while there is no national Data Stewardship programme as such in Sweden, the SND in collaboration with the University of Borås runs a course for data professionals in the data support units at Swedish universities. It is a professional development course aimed at staff from the SND Network, working in research support roles that involve RDM, DMPs and data access.

Outside Europe

We have focused on activities arising across Europe given the relationship with the EOSC. However there are similar discussions and issues arising in countries outside of the EOSC landscape, below are just two examples to illustrate this.

Australia

Broadly speaking, Australia does not have any national data skills strategy nor targeted funding for data skills as such. The national landscape presents multiple and disparate policies, at times inconsistent, across institutions, government funders, professional organisations dealing with the management and sharing of research data³⁶. Whilst there may not be a national skill strategy or targeted funding the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)³⁷ play a pivotal role in supporting FAIR data skills development through the provision of webinars and community resources.

United States

In the United States activity has focused around the GO FAIR US Office and the US Data Stewardship Competence Centre IN where the focus has been on capacity building, delivery of webinars and the establishment of a data stewardship interest group. The work is at an early stage and the aim is to extend implementation networks into the US to foster and advance data stewardship in the institutional setting. Activity has concentrated on scoping and assembling a diverse group of interested parties together to gather input and identify relevant stakeholders

³⁶ Australian Academy of Science (2021). Advancing data-intensive research in Australia

³⁷ [FAIR data - ARDC](#)

for discussion and future planning³⁸. GO FAIR US hosted a data stewardship interest group meeting³⁹ in May 2021 (the meeting was open beyond the US) which considered what the core competencies are for data stewards and what kind of data stewardship training is needed. There has been some work on developing tools for the community for re-use. For example, the FAIR Data Stewardship Plan Template for Organisations and Institutions⁴⁰ which was developed for Force 11 Scholarly Communication Institute 2020. One of the challenges for the US DSCC IN is to collaborate and build relationships in a complex national ecosystem to avoid duplication and competition with existing initiatives.

International Initiatives

The issues identified go beyond the European context with examples of similar work in many countries and regions. Additionally there are a number of international or cross region activities.

- GO FAIR
- Research Data Alliance

GO FAIR

GO FAIR⁴¹ has been working towards implementation of the FAIR principles through a number of community initiatives. One such area is Data Stewardship Competence Centres (DSCC) Implementation Network⁴² composed of national chapters that reflect local setup and needs. At present there are national chapters in Brazil, Denmark, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Poland and Switzerland. The national chapters are at different levels of development and activity (see national/regional initiatives).

³⁸ GO FAIR US Data Stewardship Interest Group Meeting and Next Steps, May 2021

<https://gofair.us/news/2021-05-8-data-stewardship-ig-mtg.html?s=0> (accessed October 2021)

³⁹ Pasquale, Valentina, Linne, Monika, Sesink, Laurents, Stryeck, Sarah, Mihai, Hannah, Pawlowska, Maria, Walek, Anna, & Giglia, Elena. (2021, June 22). Sharing FAIR Data Stewardship knowledge across borders. FAIR Festival 2021, virtual. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5115754>

⁴⁰ Kirkpatrick, Christine R.; Cragin, Melissa H.; Meyers, Natalie (2021). FAIR Data Stewardship Plan Template for Organizations and Institutions. In SDSC Research Data Services Materials Collection. UC San Diego Library Digital Collections. <https://doi.org/10.6075/J0CV4G8C>

⁴¹ [GO FAIR initiative: Make your data & services FAIR \(go-fair.org\)](https://www.go-fair.org)

⁴² <https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/dsc/>

An update on activities was presented at the GO FAIR meeting in October 2021⁴³ where national DSCCs presented updates on activities and discussion on key issues. Long term sustainability and funding of competence centres and Data Steward positions was highlighted as a key concern and still appears to be an issue for many. Even where national initiatives have provided funding for the creation of infrastructure, competence centres and data steward networks, long term funding is not guaranteed. Highlighting a need for increased stakeholder engagement particularly surrounding sustainability, as well as rewards and incentives for researchers.

Research Data Alliance

One of the core challenges that have been identified by many of the regional initiatives is the lack of clearly defined roles and responsibilities for data stewards. The **Research Data Alliance Interest Group on Professionalising Data Stewardship**⁴⁴ was recognised and endorsed in 2020 and has a number of sub-groups which are addressing a number of core themes. The IG stems from discussion around the lack of consensus on the responsibilities, knowledge and skills which can lead to confusion and hamper capacity building. Four themes have been prioritised for work so far:

- business case for data stewardship
- data stewardship terminology
- data stewardship organisational models
- training for data stewards

The number of sub-groups in this RDA IG highlights the scope of work that needs to be addressed in order to manage the challenges in the data stewardship competence landscape. The work of the IG reflects the themes that are emerging and being addressed in both project and regional activities.

Other Activities

Whilst much of the work reported on is taking place in Higher Education settings or research performing institutions the issues are not unique to these settings. Beyond the support offered by Universities and other research performing institutions that are involved in providing support for FAIR competencies, there are other players in the landscape. Examples include:

- Societies

⁴³ GO FAIR Data Stewardship Competence Centres IN National Chapters meeting, October 2021, <https://www.go-fair.org/events/data-stewardship-competence-centers-in-national-chapters-meeting/>

⁴⁴ [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG | RDA \(rd-alliance.org\)](#)

- Industry
- Collaborations
- International Non Governmental Organisations

Societies

One area for consideration is what role professional societies can play in supporting their communities. This has been noted in the TFIR report and whilst these have not been represented in the FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force an example of where Societies are contributing can be illustrated by the work of the **AGU** who are increasing the support and guidance for researchers around FAIR data in the Earth and Space Sciences specifically with their programmes to support researchers to obtain and improve skills around data management and curation with their [Data leadership | AGU](#) programme. Additionally they are playing a pivotal role with other societies in sharing knowledge between Societies with a [Data Sharing Seminar Series for Societies](#) funded by the National Science Foundation.

Industry

Another sector that perhaps has not had the same level of exposure or focus is the work undertaken in industry. An example of this is from the **Pistoia Alliance** who have a project to support FAIR⁴⁵ in the life science industry which includes the development of a FAIR Toolkit,⁴⁶ a combination of information on methods, use cases, resources and training.

Collaborations

There is also work on FAIR and activities relating to FAIR competences in other types of organisational collaborations an example of which is the work of the **European Joint Programme for Rare Diseases** (EJP RD) and their guidance on FAIR principles⁴⁷. Whilst the work might not be described as a competence center the activities they support, guidance, training, tools and a helpdesk fit within the characteristics of a competence centre focused on a specific community.

International non-governmental organisations

At the worldwide international level, the United Nation-led initiative **The United Nations Working Group on Data Stewardship**⁴⁸ has been established by the United Nations Statistical

⁴⁵ [The FAIR Toolkit and FAIR Life Science Industry Implementation Project \(pistoiaalliance.org\)](#)

⁴⁶ [FAIR Toolkit – The FAIR Toolkit by Pistoia Alliance – A FAIR Toolkit for Life Science Industry](#)

⁴⁷ [FAIR Guidance – EJP RD – European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases \(ejprarediseases.org\)](#)

⁴⁸ <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/undataforum/blog/defining-data-stewardship/>

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Commission in an effort to find a harmonisation in the definition and role of data stewardship. The Working group is expected to develop recommendations with member states, data producers, and other stakeholders on data stewardship. It is worth noting that the UN WG on Data Stewardship is an entity nested within the UN Statistics Division whose main role is to compile and disseminate global statistical information, develop standards and norms for statistical activities, and support countries' efforts to strengthen their national statistical systems. Therefore, at this stage, the UN WG approach in addressing issues related to Data Stewardship is to be understood within that specific context of the UN Statistical Division's role.

It is also worth noting that this is a relatively recent initiative whose maturity is at a learning and emerging level. However, given the global mission and impact of the organisation and the UN's influence, the WG on Data Stewardship's efforts in developing a common framework for understanding issues pertaining to Data Stewardship are to be closely followed.

Emerging themes and ongoing challenges

This report provides a short overview of some of the activities in the areas of data stewardship, FAIR skills and competencies landscape. It is not intended or possible to be comprehensive given the dynamic and changing nature of the landscape, but shows the range of activities in EOSC projects, as well as regional and international activities that contribute to the body of knowledge and experience in this field. Whilst there has been considerable activity in recent years there remains some key core themes and challenges that continue to be addressed through ongoing engagement and activities.

Collaboration:

One of the key themes coming through the activities is the extent of collaboration that there is in the FAIR competence landscape at national, regional and international levels. Challenges for some have focused on how to avoid unnecessary duplication or competition with other initiatives, whilst identifying areas where activities can complement and learn from each other. Many of the examples show a regional approach to collaboration with local implementation within a broader national framework or context. We also see a trend for the development of local networks and peer-to-peer support for practitioners in organisations. Some of these collaborations and networks are more informal at a fledgling stage whilst others, such as those in the Netherlands, are more advanced and formalised. Many of the projects are already working collaboratively and contributing to the international activities in both GO FAIR and the Research Data Alliance.

Local context:

A clear theme that runs through the work is the need for local context. Whilst there is much activity at regional, national and international levels there is a need for activities to be tailored to the local context, including the need for materials in local languages; this was explicitly mentioned in the work being undertaken in Serbia and is implicit in other initiatives. Feedback from discussion with the European Group of FAIR Champions also raised this as an issue that still needs to be addressed.

Related to this issue, one of the recommendations in the TFiR report (recommendation 11) highlights that training materials should themselves be FAIR and made available to enable reuse and adoption by others. As highlighted by the work in Serbia, creating materials in local languages requires more than just translation, often requiring materials to be created ex nihilo to account for local context. The issue of creating materials in local languages is perhaps not given enough attention when considering the reusability of training materials and the impact that the lack of materials in local languages has on uptake.

Defining roles and activities:

There is a lack of common and consistent definition and with it clear characterisation of roles adding to the complexity in the data stewardship competence landscape. Depending on organisations or communities, the definition of a data steward varies across the board, to include the provision of data, curation, encouraging data use, facilitating data dissemination, creating regulations and policies, or simply limited to basic data management.

The UN Data Stewardship WG highlighted the difficulty of finding consistent definitions across languages as well as between organisations within and outside the data community. Building consensus around some of the definitions would be helpful in establishing FAIR competences. The RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship IG is also looking to address these issues within the work of the group and is looking at representation from different research environments. Additionally the EOSC Association Task Force⁴⁹ on data stewardship and curricula will focus on the role of data stewards and their core activities.

Sustainability and capacity building:

Alongside the lack of clear definitions many of the activities are being undertaken as short term projects or within wider EU projects with limited funding. The sustainability and opportunities

⁴⁹ [Research Careers and Curricula | EOSC Association](#)

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for capacity building in FAIR competences is a recurring theme in all of the current activities. There is also an ongoing challenge of building both generic and discipline specific competences as both are needed. A lot of the activities (outside of the Cluster projects and thematic data centres) is currently mostly, or though not exclusively, aimed at building the competence in generic skills that can be applied across an institution. Whilst there is a lot of activity around the delivery of training and skills this issue of capacity building in many cases still needs to be addressed.

Conclusion

Since the initial work of FAIRsFAIR looking at the landscape there has been a significant increase in activity with a number of new initiatives starting or further development at national/regional level as well as consolidation of efforts that were already in place in for example thematic projects or research infrastructures. Not all these activities are formally (or even informally) named or defined as a Competence Centre but by the nature of the activities they are conducting fall within the characterisation of competence centres and are contributing to the FAIR competence landscape.

The range of activities across different regions, sectors and disciplines, highlights the significance of developing FAIR competences in the global research environment. Activities are prevalent at all levels from institution level through to global initiatives to address skills and competences.

The national/regional activities whilst at different stages of development or establishment show similarities in the services offered, all having at their core the development and embedding of FAIR competences and skills into practice and improving the skills of researchers and research support staff.

Given the complex nature of the requirements and the differences in regional, national and institutional settings alongside the need to adapt to researcher needs in different domains it is not surprising that there are ongoing challenges.

The ongoing work in institutions and organisations such as RDA, GO FAIR and the EOSC Association continues to provide scope and opportunities for stakeholders to work together to address these challenges to share best practices and strategies.

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- Research Data Alliance <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>
- SSHOC <https://sshopencloud.eu/>

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- Swedish National Data Service <https://snd.gu.se/>
- United Nations World DATA Forum <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/undataforum/>

Links to resources

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